

**A STUDY ON THE PREPARATION AND PERFORMANCE OF
CALCIUM CARBIDE SLAG FOAM TO REDUCE ACCIDENTS AND
CONSERVE CO₂ IN MINES**

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Abstract. In the process of coal mining, coal spontaneous combustion in the gob area poses serious threats to the safety of mine production. Besides, coal combustion also produces a large amount of greenhouse gas CO₂, which triggers a series of ecological environment problems. In order to solve these two problems, the idea of mineralizing CO₂ with the alkaline industrial waste calcium carbide slag and then sending the foams to the gob area for coal spontaneous combustion prevention was proposed in this study. First, the effects of calcium carbide slag foaming under the action of different types of foaming agents, including sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS), polyoxyethylene fatty alcohol sodium sulfate (AES), and octyl decyl glucoside (APG0810), were tested and analyzed. Furthermore, the effects of water glass (WG), sodium alginate (SA), polyvinyl alcohol 1799 (PVA), cement, and silica micro-powder on the foam stability were analyzed by investigating the stability

coefficient and drainage volume of calcium carbide slag foam. On this basis, the configuration scheme of calcium carbide slag foam with high efficiency and good stability was determined. The experimental results on CO₂ mineralization and coal spontaneous combustion inhibition reveal that the prepared calcium carbide slag foam can rapidly absorb CO₂. Moreover, after calcium carbide slag foam treatment, the spontaneous combustion tendency of the coal sample is significantly reduced.

Keywords: CO₂, Calcium carbide, sodium sulfate, slag, solve.

Introduction. According to the report of the international non-government organization “Global Carbon Project”, the global CO₂ emissions reached 37 billion tons in 2019. Due to the rapid industrialization, CO₂ emission in China is significantly enhanced and occupies about 25% of the world's total amount [1]. A large quantity of carbon emissions will lead to problems such as the rise of sea level, the decrease of freshwater and extreme climate [2–4], posing serious threats to the ecological environment and human life and health. Thus, it is of great importance to explore efficient technologies to reduce carbon emissions. Some scholars found that calcium-based adsorption materials, like calcium carbide slag, an industrial waste mainly composed of calcium hydroxide, are prospective decarburization materials. For example, Yang et al. reported that calcium carbide slag captured CO₂ by means of calcium cycling technology, concluding that calcium carbide slag still possessed high CO₂ capture capacity and stability after 20 calcination carbon cycles [5]. Sun et al. successfully improved the performance of calcium carbide slag pellets in cyclic capture of CO₂ by adopting four common waste plastics and rubber as pore-making templates and adding chlorine-free plastics and rubber plastics to change the porosity of calcium carbide slag pellets [6]. Sun et al. proved that the CO₂ capture capability of calcium carbide slag modified by propionic acid was significantly promoted in multiple calcination carbon cycles [7].

Currently, coal is still one of the main energy sources and industrial raw materials in the world. However, coal spontaneous combustion disasters easily occur in the gob

area during coal mining [8–12], producing a large quantity of toxic gases and triggering gas and coal dust explosions. Ultimately, it may lead to the occurrence of major fatal accidents. Oxygen required for spontaneous combustion of residual coal in the gob area comes from air leakage from the working face to the gob area. At present, there are many methods to prevent coal spontaneous combustion [13–15], among which the main methods are injecting inert gas CO₂ into the gob area [16] to reduce the oxygen concentration [17] in it and pouring leakage stoppage materials [18,19] into the gob area to block air leakage passages.

Given the need for inert gas CO₂ and leakage stoppage materials for preventing coal spontaneous combustion disasters in the gob area and the excellent CO₂ adsorption performance of calcium carbide slag [20,21], it is necessary to study the integrated calcium carbide slag technology for CO₂ emission reduction and coal fire disaster prevention. To achieve this goal, the pivotal issue to be considered is to ensure the efficient transportation and wide distribution of calcium carbide slag to the gob area. The distance between the ground and the underground gob area is about 1–5 km. Transporting calcium carbide slag slurry through pipelines in such a long distance [22] is prone to pipe blockage and pipe wear [23,24], due to the high density of calcium carbide slag and other reasons. In addition, the goaf area is large, generally up to 1 km long and over 100 m wide. Calcium carbide slag slurry can hardly diffuse perfectly in the gob area, resulting in the low utilization rate of calcium carbide slag slurry. Consequently, it is hard to realize large-scale CO₂ mineralization and block air leakage sufficiently. Ensuring efficient foaming and long-term foam stabilization of calcium carbide slag is the solution to this problem [25]. Efficient foaming enables calcium carbide slag to be carried by foam to realize long-distance calcium carbide slag slurry transportation through pipelines, and the long-term and large-scale flow of foam in the gob area can be achieved by improving the foam stabilization performance of calcium carbide slag foam and prolonging the decay time of foam.

This paper is aimed at finding a suitable foaming agent and foam stabilizer to

realize efficient foaming and foam stabilization of calcium carbide slag and preparing calcium carbide slag foam which can not only mineralize CO₂ but also prevent coal spontaneous combustion. In this paper, firstly, surfactants that can efficiently foam strong alkaline calcium carbide slag were selected. Then, the effects of different factors on foam stabilization were tested through the changes in the foaming volume, the drainage volume and the foam groups before and after the reaction. Furthermore, the foaming process of calcium carbide slag was explored from the microscopic perspective. Finally, the prepared calcium carbide slag foam was used for CO₂ mineralization experiment and coal spontaneous combustion inhibition experiment to verify the characteristic of calcium carbide slag foam for coal spontaneous combustion inhibition and its ability to mineralize CO₂.

Results and discussion.

Calcium carbide slag, silica micro-powder and cement were ground with a planetary ball mill, respectively. The results presented in Figs. 1, 2 suggest that the particle size distribution of raw materials. The raw materials dried in a vacuum drying oven at 40 °C for 48 h and then sealed with a sealing bag for later use. PVA is granular and difficult to dissolve in solutions due to its stable properties, and SA also tends to agglomerate in solutions. Hence, before being used, PVA and SA were respectively placed in a water bath at 85 °C and 55 °C and hydrolyzed at 300 rpm for 4 h. In view of the fact that water will evaporate after hydrolysis heating, the three-necked flask was sealed with a ground glass stopper coated with petroleum jelly. The total mass before hydrolysis is recorded as m_1 , and the total mass after hydrolysis is recorded as m_2 . After the hydrolysis is completed, the mass of water added to it is Δm , and the mixture is stirred evenly. The formula is according to Eq. (2-1).

$$\Delta m = m_1 - m_2$$

1.1.1. Calcium carbide slag foam preparation

Firstly, the foaming agent was mixed with tap water and slowly

stirred with a glass rod until the foaming agent was completely dissolved to prepare the foam solution. Then, the prepared foam solution, calcium carbide slag, cement (or silicon micro-powder) and foam stabilizer were mixed in sequence and mechanically stirred at 1700 rpm for 3 min by the Warning-Blender method to prepare calcium carbide slag foam. Foam volume test: In the process of preparing calcium carbide slag foam, the beaker calibration shall be immediately read and recorded as the foaming volume V after the mechanical stirring was finished. The experiment was repeated for 5 times in which the maximum and minimum values of the results were removed, and the average value of the rest 3 experimental results was taken as the final result.

Measurement of drainage volume and stability coefficient: After calcium carbide slag foam was prepared, it was allowed to stand for 30 min. Next, it was poured into a Buchner funnel and allowed to stand for 10 min again. Afterwards, the volume of supernatant liquid in the beaker below the funnel was measured by a measuring cylinder and recorded as the drainage volume V_1 . The total volume of liquid was V_2 . The stability coefficient S is calculated according to Eq. (2-2). Dynamic evolution of foam: The change of foam shape was continuously observed with the aid of a XSP-

8CA biological microscope (Shanghai Optical Instrument Factory, China). Firstly, a small amount of fresh calcium carbide slag foam was evenly smeared on the glass slide. Then, the hole was opened, and the magnification of objective lens, the coarse quasi-focus spiral, and the fine quasi-focus spiral were adjusted until the image got clear. After the above procedures, the foam shape was captured every 10 s.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) test: The vacuum dried calcium carbide slag, cement, silica micro-powder, and foam samples were selected for the XRD experiment by a D-MAX 2500/PC X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku Company, Japan) [34,35]. The scanning rate and range were $5^\circ/\text{min}$ 5° - 90° , respectively. Qualitative analysis was conducted on the diffraction peaks of foam and each raw material with the aid of Jade6 software to obtain their respective material compositions.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) test: WG, calcium carbide slag and foam were tested by a Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Company, the USA) [36]. After obtaining the background reference spectrum by means of KBr powder

tableting, the powdered sample and the dried KBr were added into a mortar at the ratio of 1:200 for grinding. After undergoing tableting under 10 MPa for 3 min, the tablet of mixed powder was subjected to scanning in which the wave number range was 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} and the resolution was 4 cm^{-1} . By comparing the changes of infrared spectral peaks of various raw materials and foam samples, the changes of material structure in the process of foam forming were analyzed from a microscopic perspective.

The stability of foam is affected by film drainage, and the drainage rate of film is directly correlated with the water content of foam. At the same time, adding an appropriate amount of aggregates to the foam can increase the effective viscosity of the continuous-phase liquid to slow down the drainage rate of foam, thus improving foam stability. Therefore, the effects of water-solid ratios and types of particulate matters (cement and silica micro-powder) on foam stability were studied demonstrates the

influence of different water-solid ratios on the stability coefficient, wherein the solid particles comprise 3 portions of calcium carbide slag and 1 portion of cement or silica micro-powder. As the ratio of water to solid declines, the drainage speed slows down, and the foam stability coefficient jumps distinctly. On the one hand, it is because the amount of water added is reduced, and more importantly, the particles stabilize the foam. When the particles in the solution increase, some of the particles adsorb irreversibly on the foam film surface, which improves the coalescence stability of the foam. In addition, cement, as a cementitious material, owns good adhesion. This ability enables solid particles in the foam to adhere to each other to support the foam. Besides, the hardened cement has certain strength that can improve the stability of the foam to a certain extent. However, when the water-solid ratio is 5:1, the foaming effect of the foam is poor. The foam foaming and stabilizing foam are integrated, and cement is used as the foam-stabilizing aggregate, and the water-solid ratio is 6:1.

Fig. 2

Conclusion.

The effects of different surfactants and solid particles on calcium carbide slag foaming were studied in this paper. The research results suggest that adding 0.35 wt% SDS can increase the foaming ratio of calcium carbide slag foam to 6 times. When 10 mL of 10 wt% WG, 5 wt % PVA and 1 wt% SA and 4 wt% cement are added and the water-solid ratio is 6:1, the drainage volume of foam can be reduced to 9 wt% while

the stability coefficient can be increased to 86.8%. The prepared calcium carbide slag foam can inhibit coal spontaneous combustion and mineralize CO₂ efficiently. It is expected that calcium carbide slag foam will be used for controlling the disasters in gob areas and storing a large amount of CO₂ efficiently.

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